

TWIN2EXPAND

EBDP Applicability Matrix

Deliverable 4.3

twinning towards
research excellence
in evidence-based planning
and urban design

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General Contact:

TWIN2EXPAND Project, Dr. Nadia Charalambous, Department of Architecture,
University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

For more information: charalambous.nadia@ucy.ac.cy

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1. Introduction

Evidence-based design and planning (EBDP) was brought to the fore by a seminal study by Roger Ulrich (Mullins et al. 2015) and is considered a tool to improve the performance of design solutions. The aim of the EBDP Applicability Matrix (Annex 1) is to assess whether it is feasible to apply the EBDP approach in urban design and planning projects. Feasibility is here defined in a broad way including constraints in relation to data availability and quality, tools and competences but also support from formal policy documents and stakeholders, e.g. project initiators from the public and private sector.

The EBDP Applicability Matrix can be used to assess the applicability prior to the start of the project. For example, the municipality can use it to assess bids for an urban study or development plan. In these cases, filling in the matrix is a requirement for the teams bidding for the project, which allows for a comparative EBDP analysis of the bids. The matrix can also be used within the project team to systematically assess the possibility of using an EBDP approach, even when this is not required, and identify potential challenges of various kinds from data challenges to lacking policy support.

The EBDP Applicability Matrix is composed of rows that represent the EBDP questions that can be answered by applying an EBDP approach and columns that represent the constraints (or enablers) to support the EBDP approach.

Table 1. Conceptual EBDP Applicability Matrix.

Project	Constraint 1	Constraint 2	Constraint <i>n</i>	Question Assessment
Question 1				
Question 2				
Question <i>n</i>				
Constraint Assessment				

The questions can be identified based on the design brief or discussions with the initiator (i.e. direct stakeholder) of the project. Filling in the EBDP Applicability Matrix thus always start with an interpretation of the design brief resulting in the formulation of a set of questions that allow for an assessment of the current situation (baseline study) and an evaluation of the design solutions, in line with the conceptual EBDP model (see Figure 1 and

D4.5 Research report on the applicability of EBDP). Both require spatial analysis using a Hybrid Spatial Model that includes a representation of the built environment relevant for the formulated question(s). For instance, to support active retail, restaurants and cafés on ground floor level, enough people must pass by daily. The intensity of pedestrian flow is, as we know from numerous empirical studies, supported by high street network centrality and built density. Based on this evidence, we can develop a Hybrid Spatial Model to support the design decision making. The EBDP Applicability Matrix should be capable to identify constraints in relation to this evidence as well as the required data and tools to analyse the current situation and proposed design solutions. Besides these technical constraints, the applicability of an EBDP approach is also depending on the support for it through formal policy requirements and support by direct stakeholders such as municipalities and private developers. The EBDP Applicability Matrix should thus be capable to identify both the level of technical support and the level of support by policy and stakeholders. The EBDP Applicability Matrix is thus a tool to check the applicability of EBDP for a project by answering two main questions:

1. Is there support for an EBDP approach from the stakeholder and formal policy documents?
2. Can the Hybrid Spatial Model be developed technically based on availability and quality of data and tools, known evidence that can be used as benchmark and competence?

Figure 1. Conceptual model of EBDP, developed by the Consortium based on Karimi (2021). (Based on D4.5 Research report on the applicability of EBDP)

EBDP Applicability Matrix provides a systematic assessment of the possibilities and challenges of using the EBDP approach. In case challenges are identified, it can help to identify mitigation measures. A lack of data can for instance be mitigated by buying better data, which is easier in case there is both policy and stakeholder support, including extra resources. It is therefore recommended to not focus on an overall score of applicability but instead, assess each question (horizontal assessment) and each constraint (vertical assessment) separately. This assessment can then be used to identify potential problems and discuss these with the direct stakeholders to find solutions.

2. Prototype EBDP Applicability Matrix

2.1. Matrix Structure

As discussed in above, project questions are listed in rows, while constraints are represented in columns, divided into two categories based on the two main questions we aim to answer with the EBDP Applicability Matrix. The first category involves the support for an EBDP approach by the client but also in terms of resources and formal policy. The second category covers the technical support to develop the Hybrid Spatial Model necessary for the spatial analysis and spatial evaluation. Both are discussed in more detail below.

EBDP support

- **Stakeholder support:** Is the EBDP approach required and prioritized by the direct public and/or private stakeholders (e.g. municipality, developer)?
- **Policy support:** Is there a formal policy document that requires or supports an EBDP approach and does this policy include goals and benchmarks?
- **Resources:** Are there (extra) financial resources and time available to apply the EBDP approach, especially needed when technical constraints require extra resources?

Technical EBDP constraints

- **Evidence:** Is evidence available and is this evidence quantifiable and possibly even validated based on empirical studies?
- **Data Availability and quality:** Is the necessary data available, open and of good quality (e.g. high geographic resolution, up to date)?
- **Data processing:** Is there a complete or partially automated process for data processing?
- **Tools:** Are the tools (software, hardware, infrastructure) to support the EBDP question available and open?
- **Competence:** Is the project team skilled to conduct spatial analysis and interpret the results?

2.2. Rating Scale for Applicability

To assess the support and constraints, an assessment score ranging between 0 and 3 is developed following the explanation in table 2.

Table 2. Assessment of the EBDP Applicability Matrix.

Support	Assessment score
Stakeholder support	No priority (0); low priority (1); Priority but not required (2); Priority and required (3)
Policy support	No support (0); Low support (1); Policy support but not quantified (2); Policy support with benchmarks (3)
Resources	No extra resources (0); No time constraints (1); Extra financial resources but lack of time (2); Extra financial resources and time (3)

Constraints	Assessment score
Evidence	No evidence (0); Available but not quantified (1); Quantifiable evidence (2); Validated evidence (3) ¹
Data Availability and quality	Not available (0); Available (1); Available and open (2); Available, open and high quality (3)
Data processing	Majority manual (1); Partially automated (50:50) (2); Majority automated (3)
Tools	Not available (0); Available, not open and high cost (1); Available, not open and low cost (2); Available and open (3)
Competence	Lacking skills (1); skills to conduct tasks but not to interpret results (2); skills to conduct tasks and interpret results (3)

2.3. Users' guideline of the EBDP Applicability Matrix

The use of the EBDP Applicability Matrix is simple and consists of four steps. The **first step** is to formulate the EBDP questions, identified from the design brief or discussions with the client (e.g. private developer or municipality). The questions should be formulated in such a way that they allow assessment using spatial analysis of the current situation and spatial evaluation of design proposals, in line with the EBDP conceptual model (see figure 2).

¹ Levels of evidence for design decision making (published in Pilosof and Grobman, 2021; adapted from Harris et al., 2008) from review of precedents (low level) to case studies and large-scale validated studies (high level).

Figure 2. EBDP Applicability Matrix, exemplified with CASE 1 (see also chapter 3)

The **second step** is to identify the data needed to develop the Hybrid Spatial Model based on the questions formulated in step 1. Each dataset is added as a separate sub-row in the matrix to assess ‘Data availability and quality’ and ‘Data processing’. When all questions and datasets are added to the matrix, the **third step** is to fill in the matrix. For each row, the level of support for an EBDP approach and the technical constraints are added, using the predefined lists in the matrix. For the row considering ‘Data availability and quality’ and ‘Data processing’, the user fills in the constraints per dataset. The overall score for ‘Data availability and quality’ and ‘Data processing’ is added automatically based on the median scores per dataset. The **fourth step** is to evaluate the overall scores per question and per constraint that is added automatically based on the average scores.

3. EBDP Applicability Matrix in three case studies

3.1. CASE STUDY 1. Assessing citizen services provision across urban and rural areas

This study was commissioned by the Cyprus Ministry of Transport, Communication and Works and developed in partnership with the Cyprus Post administration, which operates Citizens' Centres within select post offices. The study evaluates the locations of citizen services centres to optimise accessibility for populations across varying distances, to foster sustainable development and equitable service distribution through evidence-based planning. Using spatial analysis, the study examines existing and potential new locations for Citizens' Service Centers (KEPs) and Citizens' Centers (KEPOs), assessing the proportion of the population that can access these services from their homes at three scales: national, rural community clusters, and the urban area of Nicosia, Cyprus.

Figure 3. Example of spatial analysis CASE STUDY 1

3.1.1. Identified EBDP questions

The questions formulated to be answered using an EBDP approach are:

- How many people can reach the existing and new service points using different means of transportation? 400m, 1200m, 2000m, and 5000m for walking, cycling, driving,

respectively.

- How many people can reach the existing and new service points using public transportation? By walking 200m to 400m from each bus stop, which is connected directly by a bus route that reaches a bus stop that is 400m away from the service point.

3.1.2. Stakeholder and policy support

The Cyprus Ministry of Transport, Communications and Works commissioned this study in partnership with the Cyprus Post administration, which manages Citizens' Centres located in certain post office branches. The main goal was to assess how citizen service centres are geographically distributed, with the intention of improving access for people living in different areas. This assessment sought to advance sustainable development and ensure fair distribution of services through a data-driven spatial planning approach.

The Cyprus Post administration contributed by providing an initial study and a set of locations and scenarios for spatial analysis and evaluation. Several consultation meetings were held with key stakeholders to decide on key issues to address, to present the findings, discuss potential interventions, and explore alternative strategies. The outcomes of the spatial analysis were well-received and recognized for their analytical robustness and practical relevance. Regarding project resources, no external data or funding was provided by the stakeholders. Instead, the data sources and analytical inputs were derived as part of this research project itself.

3.1.3. Technical constraints

While the overarching policy framework and stakeholder engagement supported the adoption of an evidence-based approach, its implementation was significantly constrained by data availability and processing challenges. A primary limitation was the restricted access to high-quality data. For instance, obtaining population data at the time of the project proved difficult. Consequently, the analysis relied on open-access population density data provided by a European open data platform, which enabled continued progress.

A similar issue arose in modelling the street network. Road centerline data was sourced from open platforms and subsequently modified manually to align with the analytical requirements of the study. In relation to service point data, the limited institutional capacity to manage and structure geospatial data presented further constraints. This necessitated the manual processing of all available service point data at a national scale. Although the identification of potential new service point locations proceeded without significant obstacles, the process was expected to be manual due to the lack of systematic frameworks. Public transport data, despite being available, required considerable preprocessing to render it suitable for analysis, again highlighting the absence of standardized data handling protocols. Overall, when assessed against the need for high-quality, official, and well-documented

datasets, data availability represented a considerable constraint. Nevertheless, open-source platforms played a critical role in enabling the operationalization of the evidence-based approach.

With respect to analytical tools, most of the required software for data preparation, modeling, and analysis was accessible through open-source platforms, thus posing minimal constraints. Furthermore, the expertise necessary to carry out the tasks and interpret the results was not a limiting factor, as the work was undertaken by an academic team with specialized knowledge in evidence-based design methodologies.

3.1.4. Assessment EBDP Applicability

The applicability of the Evidence-Based Design and Planning (EBDP) approach for the citizen services centre provision project was assessed through a structured matrix addressing both technical feasibility and institutional support. Two key research questions were evaluated: the population catchment of existing and proposed service points using various transportation modes, and the same analysis using solely public transportation. The findings reveal that while evidence exists, it remains unquantified, thereby limiting its immediate analytical utility. Data availability, however, scored highly across all relevant datasets, indicating that we could manage the process due to the accessibility of open access data. Data processing posed a moderate constraint, with several datasets, particularly service point data, requiring substantial manual handling. However, the analytical competence of the research team was identified as a strong enabler for implementing the EBDP approach. From an institutional perspective, stakeholder engagement was evident, with EBDP recognised as a priority. As regards policy support, although not explicitly benchmarked, it was present. The availability of additional resources and time further reinforced the feasibility of the approach. Overall, the technical constraints averaged a score of 2.4, while institutional support scored slightly higher at 2.7, suggesting that while the foundation for applying EBDP is robust, enhancements in data quantification and automation are necessary to optimise its effectiveness (see figure 4).

PROJECT NAME: Citizen services center provision																		
	Technical EBDP Constraints										EBDP Support							
	Evidence		Data Availability		Data processing		Tools		Competence		SCORE Constraints	Stakeholder support		Policy Support		Resources		SCORE Support
Question 1 - population catchment of existing and new service points using different means of transportation	Available but not quantified	1	Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.4	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support but not quantified	2	Extra resources and time	3	2.7
Dataset 1 - Population Density			Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2												
Dataset 2 - service points			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - network			Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2												
Question 2 - population catchment of existing and new service points using public transportation	Available but not quantified	1	Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.4	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support but not quantified	2	Extra resources and time	3	2.7
Dataset 1 - population Density			Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2												
Dataset 2 - service points			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - public transport			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority automated	3												
SCORE		1.0		3.0		2.0		3.0		3.0	2.4		3.0		2.0		3.0	2.7

Figure 4. EBDP Applicability Matrix for: CASE STUDY 1

3.2. CASE STUDY 2. Assessing accessibility and connectivity to green spaces (Nicosia Linear Park)

The Pedieos Linear Park in Nicosia serves as a crucial urban green corridor, stretching over 9.5 km. It plays a vital role in enhancing urban connectivity, promoting environmental sustainability, and improving residents' quality of life. The study evaluates the park's current state and assesses the impact of a proposed masterplan designed to optimise urban connectivity, expand population reach, and ensure equitable distribution of amenities. The existing situation indicates that while the park is a well-utilised green space, it requires further enhancements to address accessibility gaps, improve safety, and better integrate public services. Within the park itself, there are multiple categories of facilities, including social, sports, animal, commercial, and general amenities, with varying degrees of accessibility and distribution. Despite a relatively high level of accessibility to the proposed activities /amenities, the spatial distribution of them remains uneven across different sections of the park, leading to disparities in the quality of experience for visitors. The stakeholder was initiated by the research group *Nicosia Intermunicipal Development Projects Company* (DAEL), which is the representative of all involved municipalities of the project, as well as having the responsibility for the master plan. Furthermore, focus groups were initiated afterwards, including residents and NGOs representatives. They emphasised the need for a well-connected, environmentally sustainable, and inclusive public space. Key priorities included improving pedestrian pathways, integrating safety measures, expanding amenities, and fostering community engagement through cultural and recreational activities.

Figure 3. Example of spatial analysis: CASE STUDY 2

3.2.1. Identified EBDP questions

The questions formulated to be answered using an EBDP approach are:

- How many people have access to the linear park? Within 1200m from the official entrance points.
- How does the accessibility to the linear park increase after the proposed interventions? (Within 1200m from the official existing and proposed entrances).
- How inclusive are the proposed activities across the linear park to all surrounding residential areas? (within 1200m from the official existing and proposed entrances).

3.2.2. Stakeholder and policy support

In this project, the research team assumed the leading role and was solely responsible for conducting the spatial analysis. The project was supported by internal resources derived from the research initiative itself. A structured methodology was adopted to actively engage

stakeholders through focus groups and workshops conducted both prior to and following the analytical phases. This participatory approach aimed to integrate stakeholders' insights, needs, and perceptions regarding the current state of the park and to inform the development of the research questions and of proposed interventions from their perspective. The overall process was largely driven by the research team's initiative and commitment to advancing an evidence-based planning approach. Despite the project lacking a formal policy paper, the stakeholder initiative was supportive. And the needed resources were provided by this project itself.

3.2.3. Technical constraints

This project encountered similar challenges to the previous case, particularly regarding the availability of population data and the modelling of the street network. Additional constraints emerged from the lack of accessible data on the park's existing entrances and the distribution of current amenities and activities along its length. As a result, this information had to be collected manually through fieldwork, which required both time and resources. Furthermore, although the proposed interventions were provided by the municipality, they were not publicly accessible and were delivered in non-editable formats such as images and text. This necessitated manual processing to integrate the interventions into the street network model and to spatially map the proposed activities within the park. In contrast, as with the previous case study, no constraints were identified in terms of the tools and technical competencies required for the spatial analysis.

3.2.4. Assessment EBDP Applicability

The applicability of the evidence-based design and planning (EBDP) approach in the Linear Park project is influenced by a combination of technical feasibility and institutional support, as detailed in the EBDP Applicability Matrix. On the technical front, the project displays moderate feasibility across all three analytical questions, with constraint scores ranging from 2.0 to 2.6. This is primarily due to the availability of validated evidence, open access to relevant datasets, and a project team capable of conducting and interpreting spatial analyses using appropriate tools. Nonetheless, technical limitations persist, particularly in the realm of data processing, which remains mostly manual for several key datasets such as entrances and street networks. These constraints affect the efficiency and scalability of the analytical process. Notably, the third question, which evaluates the spatial distribution of proposed activities within the park, received the lowest score (2.0), largely due to less quantifiable evidence and lower data reliability.

In contrast, institutional support for EBDP is notably limited. Although stakeholder interest exists, indicated by prioritization of EBDP without a formal requirement, there is no supportive policy framework. As for resources, this project was also part of this research project itself, where it is allocated to facilitate EBDP implementation. As a result, EBDP support scores remain low and consistent across all questions, averaging 1.7. This disparity between moderate technical capacity and minimal institutional backing suggests that, while the technical means to apply EBDP are in place, the absence of policy mandates and resource allocation substantially limits the approach’s broader impact and sustainability. Addressing these institutional shortcomings will be essential for embedding EBDP more effectively into future urban planning practices (see figure 6).

PROJECT NAME: Linear Park																			
	Technical EBDP Constraints											EBDP Support							
	Evidence		Data Availability		Data processing		Tools		Competence		SCORE Constraints	Stakeholder support		Policy Support		Resources		SCORE Support	
Question 1 - Assessing the existing population catchment to the linear park	Validated evidence	3	Available and open	2	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.6	Priority but EBDP not required	2	No policy support	0	Extra resources and time	3	1.7	
<i>Dataset 1 - Population Density</i>			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2													
<i>Dataset 2 - Entrances</i>			Available	1	Majority manually	1													
<i>Dataset 3 - network</i>			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2													
Question 2 - Assessing the proposed interventions aiming to increase the population catchment to the linear park	Validated evidence	3	Available and open	2	Majority manually	1	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.4	Priority but EBDP not required	2	No policy support	0	Extra resources and time	3	1.7	
<i>Dataset 1 - Population Density</i>			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2													
<i>Dataset 2 - New Entrances</i>			Available	1	Majority manually	1													
<i>Dataset 3 - Modified network</i>			Available and open	2	Majority manually	1													
Question 3 - Assessing the spatial distribution of proposed activities within the linear park to residence areas	Available but not quantified	1	Available	1	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.0	Priority but EBDP not required	2	No policy support	0	Extra resources and time	3	1.7	
<i>Dataset 1 - Residence buildings</i>			Available	1	Majority automated	3													
<i>Dataset 2 - Activities points</i>			Available	1	Majority manually	1													
<i>Dataset 3 - network</i>			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2													
SCORE		2.3		1.7		1.7		3.0		3.0	2.3		2.0		0.0		3.0	1.7	

Figure 6. EBDP Applicability Matrix for CASE STUDY 2

3.3. CASE STUDY 3. Assessing Urban Accessibility in the 'Land of Tomorrow' Master Plan

Ensuring equitable access to spaces, services, and amenities becomes a critical challenge as populations grow and urban landscapes evolve. The assessment of the «Land of Tomorrow» project addresses this challenge by evaluating the spatial and functional efficacy of a proposed masterplan. The study focuses on two core dimensions: accessibility, which determines how easily residents can navigate and utilise urban spaces, and reach, which assesses connectivity to essential Points of Interest (POIs) such as transit hubs, cycling lanes, and community facilities. By integrating advanced spatial analysis techniques, the project aims to identify strengths and gaps in the proposed urban design, ensuring it aligns with broader goals of sustainability, inclusivity, and resilience.

Figure 7. Example of spatial analysis: CASE STUDY 3

3.3.1. Identified EBDP questions

The questions formulated to be answered using an EBDP approach are:

- How are pedestrian flows anticipated to be distributed in the streets before and after the proposed interventions? Street centrality is utilised within walking distance (i.e. 400m, 800m) as a proxy for pedestrian flows.
- Where can commercial land uses in relation to pedestrian flows be expected? Through testing the proposed location, overlapping the street centrality measurements within walking distances.

3.3.2. Stakeholder and policy support

The primary stakeholder in this project was the local consultant. We engaged with their team both before and after conducting our analysis to understand their reflections and requirements. They expressed strong support for key benchmarks aimed at promoting a sustainable and well-integrated development, not only in terms of pedestrian infrastructure and walkability, but also concerning the ecological and environmental dimensions of Larnaca's waterfront. For the required resources, this project followed the previous projects, where it was enabled using this research project, as an external fund to the research team.

3.3.3. Technical constraints

In this project, the primary constraints are related to data availability and processing requirements. As a meso- to micro-scale study, data were provided by the project's local consultant. However, the format of the data necessitated manual modelling of both the street network and the proposed land use points. In other words, while the data were accessible, they were not openly available, and substantial effort was required to prepare them for analysis. Like the two previous case studies, there were no limitations regarding tools or technical expertise in this project.

3.3.4. Assessment EBDP Applicability

The EBDP Applicability Matrix for the Larnaca Waterfront project highlights a slight distinction between strong institutional support and limited technical capability, especially regarding data handling. On the institutional front, the evidence-based design and planning (EBDP) approach is fully integrated and actively supported. Both analytical questions, one assessing pedestrian-scale movement through proposed street networks and the other evaluating the spatial relationship of commercial land use to centrality, achieve the highest possible support scores (3.0). This reflects not only high stakeholder engagement, where EBDP is both a priority and a requirement, but also robust policy backing that includes defined benchmarks and the provision of extra time and resources.

Technically, the project is anchored in strong evidence, with validated data and competent staff scoring 3.0 across those categories. Essential tools for spatial analysis are also readily accessible and well-supported. However, the feasibility of the technical implementation is limited by the data processing capabilities. Although the relevant datasets exist, they are often not open, and data processing is largely manual, resulting in low scores (1.0) in both categories. This presents a time efficiency constraint on the project’s ability to effectively execute EBDP (see figure 8). In summary, while the institutional environment for EBDP is exemplary, supported by mandates, benchmarks, and resource commitments, the technical execution is hindered by outdated or labour-intensive data workflows. Addressing these constraints through improved data infrastructure and automation will be crucial to translating institutional enthusiasm into impactful spatial planning results.

PROJECT NAME: Larnaca waterfront																		
	Technical EBDP Constraints										EBDP Support							
	Evidence		Data Availability		Data processing		Tools		Competence		SCORE Constraint s	Stakeholder support		Policy Support		Resources		SCORE Support
Question 1 - Assessing proposed street network for pedestrian-scale movement	Validated evidence	3	Available	1	Majority manually	1	Available and open	3	Skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.2	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support with benchmarks	3	Extra resources and time	3	3.0
Dataset 1 - Proposed network			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 2 - City's network			Available and open	2	Majority automated	3												
Question 2 - Assessing the spatial location of commercial land use in relation to the centrality measurements	Validated evidence	3	Available	1	Majority manually	1	Available and open	3	Skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.2	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support with benchmarks	3	Extra resources and time	3	3.0
Dataset 1 - Proposed network			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 2 - Activities points			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - City's network			Available and open	2	Majority automated	3												
SCORE		3.0		1.0		1.0		3.0		3.0	2.2		3.0		3.0		3.0	3.0

Figure 8. EBDP Applicability Matrix for CASE STUDY 3

ANNEX 1

Prototype EBDP Matrix

Fields to fill in:
 [ADD TEXT]
 Drop down menu

Automated fields:
 Overall score
 Cell score

Instructions:

1. Formulate the EBDP questions; If more/less than two questions are formulated, add/remove rows and copy-paste the formulas from an existing row
2. Identify the data needed to develop the Hybrid Spatial Model based on the questions formulated in step 1; If more/less datasets are identified, add/remove new rows and copy-paste the formulas from an existing row
3. Fill in the matrix using the drop down menus; For the row considering 'Data availability and quality' and 'Data processing', the user fills in the constraints per dataset
4. Always check the formulas used for overall and cell score when rows are added or removed to ensure all filled in values are included

PROJECT NAME: [ADD TEXT]																		
	Evidence	EBDP Constraints									EBDP Support							
		Data Availability		Data processing		Tools		Competence		SCORE Constraints	Stakeholder support		Policy Support		Resources		SCORE Support	
Question 1 - [ADD TEXT]	Available but not quantified	1	Available	1	Partially automated	2	Not available	0	Lacking skills	1	1.0	No priority	0	No policy support	0	No extra resources	0	0.0
Dataset I - [ADD TEXT]			Not available	0	Majority manually	1												
Dataset II - [ADD TEXT]			Available and open	2	Majority automated	3												
Question 2 - [ADD TEXT]	Available but not quantified	1	Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2	Not available	0	Lacking skills	1	1.4	No priority	0	No policy support	0	No extra resources	0	0.0
Dataset I - [ADD TEXT]			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority manually	1												
Dataset II - [ADD TEXT]			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority automated	3												
SCORE		1.0		2.0		2.0		0.0		1.0	1.2		0.0		0.0		0.0	0.0

Rating Scale for Applicability

Evidence	No evidence Available but not quantified Available and quantifiable Validated evidence
Data Availability	Not available Available Available and open Available, open and high quality
Data processing	Majority manually Partially automated Majority automated
Tools	Not available Available, not open, high cost Available, not open, low cost Available and open
Competence	Lacking skills Skills to conduct tasks but not to interpret results Skills to conduct tasks and interpret results
Stakeholder Support	No priority Low priority Priority but EBDP not required Priority and EBDP required
Policy Support	No policy support Low support Policy support but not quantified Policy support with benchmarks
Resources	No extra resources No time constraints Extra financial resources Extra resources and time

Prototype EBDP Matrix

Fields to fill

In:

[ADD TEXT]

Drop down menu

Automated

fields:

Overall score

Cell score

Instructions:

1. Formulate the EBDP questions; If more/less than two questions are formulated, add/remove rows and copy-paste the formulas from an existing row
2. Identify the data needed to develop the Hybrid Spatial Model based on the questions formulated in step 1; If more/less datasets are identified, add/remove new rows and copy-paste the formulas from an existing row
3. Fill in the matrix using the drop down menus; For the row considering 'Data availability and quality' and 'Data processing', the user fills in the constraints per dataset
4. Always check the formulas used for overall and cell score when rows are added or removed to ensure all filled in values are included

PROJECT NAME: Citizen services center provision																		
	Evidence	Data Availability	Technical EBDP Constraints						SCORE Constraints	EBDP Support								
			Data processing	Tools	Competence	Stakeholder support	Policy Support	Resources		SCORE Support								
Question 1 - population catchment of existing and new service points using different means of transportation	Available but not quantified	1	Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.4	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support but not quantified	2	Extra resources and time	3	2.7
Dataset 1 - Population Density			Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2												
Dataset 2 - service points			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - network			Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2												
Question 2 - population catchment of existing and new service points using public transportation	Available but not quantified	1	Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.4	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support but not quantified	2	Extra resources and time	3	2.7
Dataset 1 - population Density			Available, open and high quality	3	Partially automated	2												
Dataset 2 - service points			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - public transport			Available, open and high quality	3	Majority automated	3												
SCORE		1.0		3.0		2.0		3.0		3.0	2.4		3.0		2.0		3.0	2.7

PROJECT NAME: Linear Park																		
	Evidence	Data Availability	Technical EBDP Constraints						SCORE Constraints	EBDP Support								
			Data processing	Tools	Competence	Stakeholder support	Policy Support	Resources		SCORE Support								
Question 1 - Assessing the existing population catchment to the linear park	Validated evidence	3	Available and open	2	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.6	Priority but EBDP not required	2	No policy support	0	Extra resources and time	3	1.7
Dataset 1 - Population Density			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2												
Dataset 2 - Entrances			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - network			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2												
Question 2 - Assessing the proposed interventions aiming to increase the population catchment to the linear park	Validated evidence	3	Available and open	2	Majority manually	1	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.4	Priority but EBDP not required	2	No policy support	0	Extra resources and time	3	1.7
Dataset 1 - Population Density			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2												
Dataset 2 - New Entrances			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - Modified network			Available and open	2	Majority manually	1												
Question 3 - Assessing the spatial distribution of proposed activities within the linear park to residence areas	Available but not quantified	1	Available	1	Partially automated	2	Available and open	3	skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.0	Priority but EBDP not required	2	No policy support	0	Extra resources and time	3	1.7
Dataset 1 - Residence buildings			Available	1	Majority automated	3												
Dataset 2 - Activities points			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - network			Available and open	2	Partially automated	2												
SCORE		2.3		1.7		1.7		3.0		3.0	2.3		2.0		0.0		3.0	1.7

PROJECT NAME: Larnaca waterfront																		
	Evidence	Data Availability	Technical EBDP Constraints						SCORE Constraints	EBDP Support								
			Data processing	Tools	Competence	Stakeholder support	Policy Support	Resources		SCORE Support								
Question 1 - Assessing proposed street network for pedestrian-scale movement	Validated evidence	3	Available	1	Majority manually	1	Available and open	3	Skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.2	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support with benchmarks	3	Extra resources and time	3	3.0
Dataset 1 - Proposed network			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 2 - City's network			Available and open	2	Majority automated	3												
Question 2 - Assessing the spatial location of commercial land use in relation to the centrality measurements	Validated evidence	3	Available	1	Majority manually	1	Available and open	3	Skills to conduct tasks and interpret results	3	2.2	Priority and EBDP required	3	Policy support with benchmarks	3	Extra resources and time	3	3.0
Dataset 1 - Proposed network			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 2 - Activities points			Available	1	Majority manually	1												
Dataset 3 - City's network			Available and open	2	Majority automated	3												
SCORE		3.0		1.0		1.0		3.0		3.0	2.2		3.0		3.0		3.0	3.0

Rating Scale for Applicability

Evidence	No evidence Available but not quantified Available and quantifiable Validated evidence
Data Availability	Not available Available Available and open Available, open and high quality
Data processing	Majority manually Partially automated Majority automated
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